

Table 3. Immunogenic peptides encoded by circRNAs.

Micropeptides sequence name	Cancers	circRNA symbol	circRNA name	Neoantigens sequences binding HLA I	Neoantigens sequences binding HLA II	References
FBXW7-185AA	Glioma and triple negative breast cancer	<i>FBXW7</i>	F-box and WD repeat domain containing 7	SPFYTKTTKDY FYTKTTKDY TKTTKDYFL KTTKDYFLRI TTKDYFLRI YFLRIDCQKW LRIDCQKWSY RIDCQKWSY	DYFLRIDCQKWSY DYFLRIDCQKWSYW DYFLRIDCQKWSYWV DYFLRIDCQKWSYWVR KDYFLRIDCQKWSY KDYFLRIDCQKWSYW KDYFLRIDCQKWSYWV YFLRIDCQKWSYWVR LSSPFYTKTTKDYF LSSPFYTKTTKDYFL LSSPFYTKTTKDYFL LSSPFYTKTTKDYFLR LSSPFYTKTTKDYFLR LSSPFYTKTTKDYFLRI LSSPFYTKTTKDYFLRID SPFYTKTTKDYFL SPFYTKTTKDYFLR SPFYTKTTKDYFLRI SPFYTKTTKDYFLRID SSPFYTKTTKDYF SSPFYTKTTKDYFL SSPFYTKTTKDYFL SSPFYTKTTKDYFLR SSPFYTKTTKDYFLRI	[75]
circFAM53B-219	Breast cancer	<i>FAM53B</i>	family with sequence similarity 53 member B	ALFRLTNRA RTAHYGTGR	GNALFRLTNRAPASG KMTDGETWTGNALFRLTNRAPASG- NACLKRTAHYGTGRQ	38093017